

Ganasowada to Canasawacta

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Why is the creek, that flows through 5 of our 21 towns, named “Canasawacta”?

The Canasawacta Creek has two named branches. The east branch begins in Otselic and flows through Smyrna. The west branch begins in Pharsalia. Both branches converge in Plymouth and flow into Norwich, merging with the Chenango River at the southern tip of the City of Norwich. County Road 16 runs along the east branch and State Route 23 runs along the west branch (1) (Fig. 1).

The 1789 survey map of the Twenty Townships clearly names the “Canasewachte Creek” in Town 11 (Plymouth) as it flows into Town 15 (Norwich). It also assigns this name to a location where this Creek turns from flowing southerly to flowing easterly, prior to its confluence with the Chenango River (2) (Fig. 2).

The 1851 map of Lewis H. Morgan shows the name “GÄNASOWÄDA” at this same place (3) (Fig. 3). While the spelling may be deceptive, the pronunciation is not. “Ganasowada” sounds similar to “Canasawacta.” The “Ä” is pronounced as the “a” in “far,” according to the key on Morgan’s map. Local Native Americans did not have a written language, so all spellings were concocted by Euro-Americans who wrote the words the way they heard them.

The 1943 topographic map shows this knoll as a circular contour line of 1020 feet, with the Canasawacta Creek between 1000 and 990 feet (4) (Fig. 4). The 1903 edition does not.

This Canasawacta Knoll is in the Mount Hope Cemetery and is very obvious from State Route 12 and from the City parking lot in South Broad Street Park (across from McDonald’s). See photo (Fig. 5). This knoll has

Figure 1. Map of the Canasawacta Creek from origins to Chenango River. Dot west of confluence is the Knoll. M = McDonough, NN = North Norwich. NO = Norwich. O = Otselic. PH = Pharsalia. PL = Plymouth. PR = Preston. S = Smyrna.

several old graves atop it, the earliest being 1806. This knoll may have been taller then than it is now.

The earliest publication I have found describing this place is by Hiram C. Clark in his 1850 history book. He tells the story of Casper M. Rouse, the landowner, who started to dig a cellar hole for an intended house and uncovered “human bones in such great numbers as to deter Mr. Rouse from the further execution of his enterprise, and it was accordingly abandoned. The bones were discovered in an upright position or nearly so.” Clark obtained this information from General Thompson Meade, who came to Chenango in 1792 (5).

This knoll was described by the late Ruby Adams (1923–2002) in an unpublished, undated, typewritten manuscript. She also states that this place was an Indian burial ground, but does not reveal her source (6).

The name “Canasawacta” is alleged to mean “cabin between two other

Figure 2. DeWitt Clinton 1789 Survey map, Town 15. Note “Canasawachte.” Dotted line in lower two great lots is the overland Iroquois Trail connecting the Chenango and Unadilla rivers.

Figure 3. Morgan map of 1851 showing “GĀNASOWĀDA.”

Figure 4. Topographic map, Norwich NY, 1943, showing knoll as circular contour line (1020 feet) below “W” in NORWICH.

cabins” (7). It could indeed mean that, but it could also have some other, metaphorical meanings. Perhaps it was a landmark between two other settlements. Or, because this knoll was a burial mound, it could mean the place where a body lies in repose between this life and its afterlife.

I wonder if the wider area around the confluence could have been called “Canasawacta.” The 1789 surveyor’s field book calls the Indian Castle the “Cannasewachta Castle” (8). Documentation for the Indian Castle itself is provided by A. Gail Merian (9).

The flat area south of the Canasawacta Creek and west of the Chenango River is known as the “Jamba Flats,” an unofficial nickname. It has been well researched because this area was required to be studied prior to constructing the City of Norwich Waste Water Treatment Facility, which first opened in 1989 (10). The literature describing the archaeological research here is presented as a bibliography (11). Its history appears in a quick overview (12).

The Johnson Creek is the connection between the Jamba Flats and another well researched area, the White Site, a pre-Iroquois settlement near the northeastern border of the Town of Norwich (13). The Johnson Creek

Figure 5. North side of the Canasawacta Knoll in Mount Hope Cemetery, Norwich. Photo taken on 19 December 2017.

flows into the Chenango River from the east, often as a multi-braided delta, just south of the Canasawacta Creek entry and north of the Castle (14). This nexus of creeks and the river, now called the hamlet of Polkville, was the western terminus of the famous “Iroquois Trail,” which ran between Polkville and the Unadilla River. It is the shortest distance between the Chenango and the Unadilla rivers. Today this trail is approximated by County Road 33 and White Store Road.

On the Morgan map (Fig. 3) south of “GÄNASOWÄDA” is the name “SO-DE A-LO-WÄ-NAKE,” which seems to be at the confluence of the Fly-Meadow Creek and the Chenango River, just north of the Village of Oxford and its Fort Hill, described by Clark (5).

My conclusion is that the Jamba Flats area was called “Ganasowada” by its Native American inhabitants and we now call and spell it “Canasawacta.” I suspect that it was a prehistoric central social and commercial hub with traffic north and south on both rivers (Chenango and Unadilla) and east and west by both creeks (Canasawacta and Johnson) and all connected by the overland trail.

Endnotes

1. Gibbon, Randy W. *Map of Chenango County New York*. Norwich, NY: Chenango County Department of Public Works, 2001.

2. DeWitt, Simeon. *A Field-Book of the First Fifteen of 20 Townships in the Oneida Country Surveyed Pursuant to an Act of the State Passed the 25th Feb/1789*. Albany, NY: Surveyor General's Office 1 May 1990. Map.

3. Morgan, Lewis H. *Map of Ho-De-No-Sau-Nee-Ga or the Territories of the People of the Long House in 1720: exhibiting the home country of the Iroquois with the aboriginal names of their villages, lakes, rivers, streams & ancient localities, and the courses of their principal trails*. Albany, NY: R.H. Pease. 1851. hdl.huntington.org/cdm/ref/collection/p15150coll4/id/6998 (accessed on 31 December 2017).

4 Anon. *Topographic map Norwich, N. Y.* 7.5 minute. Washington, DC: United States Geologic Survey. 1943.

5. Clark, Hiram C. [Norwich village cemetery.] In: *History of Chenango County, containing the Divisions of the County and Sketches of the Towns; Indian Tribes and Titles; Gov. Clinton's Purchase of the County Townships, Early Inhabitants and Settlements; Also: Land Patents; Rise and Progress of Agriculture, Manufactures and Trade; Annals of the Chenango Canal; Church History; Eminent Men and Statesmen, Professions, Etc. Etc.* Norwich, NY: Thompson & Pratt. 1850. Page 16.

6. Adams, Ruby. Mount Hope Cemetery. Unpublished, undated, typewritten manuscript.

7. Bright, William. CANASAWACTA in: *Native American Placenames of the United States*. Norman, OK: University of Oklahoma Press. 2004. Page 79.

8. DeWitt, Simeon. *A Field-Book of the First Fifteen of 20 Townships in the Oneida Country Surveyed Pursuant to an Act of the State Passed the 25th Feb/1789*. Albany, NY: Surveyor General's Office 1 May 1990. Page 143.

9. Merian, A. Gail. Documenting the Indian Castle. *Journal of the Chenango County Historical Society* 2017 Summer; 6: 35–45.

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12. Windsor, Donald A. Our oldest cornfield. In: *Souvenirs of Yesteryear. Exploring Chenango County, New York*. Norwich, NY: SciAesthetics. Volume 3 pages 28–29.

13. Windsor, Donald A. Bibliography—the White Site. *Chenango Archaeologist* 2008–2009 Winter; 1(3): 2.

14. Windsor, Donald A. Confluence of Johnson Creek and the Chenango River. *chenangoarchaeologists.blogspot.com* Posting on 10 April 2012 Tuesday. (accessed on 13 July 2018)